

Epidemiology of Vestibular Migraine in Patients with Dizziness presenting to the ENT clinic in Singapore using ICHD-3b Vestibular Migraine diagnostic criteria

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Abstract:

Background: Vertigo and migraine are frequent complaints in the primary care setting. Worldwide, lifetime prevalence is between 17 to 30% and 13 to 30% respectively. The clinical association between vertigo and migraine has gained traction over the past few decades as a clinical entity more than chance co-occurrence, and vestibular migraine (VM) which is the combination of vertigo, dizziness and balance disturbance with migraine has an expanding body of research which have found it to be among one of the top causes of recurrent spontaneous vertigo. However, a study on the epidemiology and prevalence of VM has yet to be done in Singapore. The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of VM amongst patients presenting to the ENT outpatient clinic with dizziness based on the ICHD-3B criteria, and to compare differences between VM and non-VM patients.

Methods: This is a prospective cross-sectional study conducted on 307 patients presenting to the Tan Tock Seng Hospital Ear Nose and Throat clinic in Singapore for consultation for dizziness over a 6-week period from August to November 2018. A questionnaire was administered to collect epidemiological data, dizziness and headache symptoms as well as impact on quality of life. Definite and probable VM was diagnosed from the questionnaire according to the Consensus Diagnostic Criteria mutually accepted by the International Headache Society and Bárány Society and incorporated into the new International Classification of Headache Disorders (ICHD)-3 beta version of headache classification. Impact on quality of life was assessed with the Migraine Disability Scale (MIDAS), Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) and Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS). Statistical analysis was performed using Stata. Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess data normality and comparison between VM and non-VM groups were made using t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous data, and Chi-squared or Fischer's exact test for categorical data.

Results: Of the 307 patients presenting to the ENT clinic with dizziness, 70 (22.8%) were found to have probable VM while 83 (27.0%) were found to have definite VM. The study population was predominantly female (64.8%), with a mean age of 61 years. Patients with VM are associated with a younger age of presentation. There was a significantly higher proportion of VM patients with a history of motion sickness and familial history of first degree relatives with dizziness and headache compared to non-VM patients. VM was also associated with comorbidity and decrease quality of life, with significantly increased DHI and DASS scores across all 3 categories for Depression, Anxiety and Stress ($P < .001$).

Conclusion: Subjective complaints of headache appears to accompany dizziness relatively often, and VM is a prevalent condition in patients presenting with dizziness to the TSSH ENT clinic in Singapore. It is important to be aware of the prevalence of VM and familiar in making the diagnosis to enable early treatment and improve quality of life for patients.

Nasopharyngeal Sarcoidosis: A rare location Involvement and A forgotten Entity

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Abstract:

Aims:

Sarcoidosis is a chronic, multi-system, non-caseating granulomatous lesion of unknown etiology. It usually has pulmonary presentation. Involvement of upper respiratory tract, nasopharynx and waldeyer's ring is very rare and sparsely reported in literature.

Objective:

Objective of this report is to evaluate a rare involvement of Sarcoidosis in nasopharynx. The purpose of this report is to discuss the clinical presentation, method of diagnosis and treatment for nasopharyngeal as well as upper respiratory tract Sarcoidosis.

Method:

A 38 yr. old female came with the chief complaints of nasal obstruction, snoring and headache. Nasal endoscopic examination revealed soft, polypoidal mass in nasopharynx at the roof, giving clinical suspicion of adenoid hypertrophy. CT PNS showed polypoidal mass in nasopharynx.

Excision biopsy of mass was planned. Histopathological examination revealed non-caseating granulomatous lesion. AFB staining failed to show tuberculous bacilli. Serum ACE levels were markedly raised. From this, diagnosis of Sarcoidosis was made.

Patient was started on topical steroid nasal spray and systemic corticosteroids. Patient responded well. Follow up after 6 months showed no relapse of symptoms and no regrowth of mass.

Conclusion:

Sarcoidosis usually has pulmonary presentation. Extra pulmonary organs most commonly affected are lymph nodes, eyes and skin. Nasopharyngeal involvement is very rare.

However, differential diagnosis of Sarcoidosis should be kept in mind for nasopharyngeal mass. Currently practiced line of treatment for Sarcoidosis is immunosuppressive therapy with corticosteroids. Local treatment may provide some temporary symptomatic relief; however, long-term systemic anti-inflammatory treatment is often required. Recent advances in the treatment of sarcoidosis have led to new therapeutic options for these frequently refractory conditions.

Ossiculoplasty Why bother?

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Abstract:

Reconstruction of the ossicular chain for the restoration of hearing is one of the most rewarding areas of otology but can also be one of the most challenging and on occasions frustrating. In this practical lecture a brief and humbling look at the history of middle ear surgery will serve as a reminder of the immense shoulders on which we all stand. The patient and pathological obstacles that stand in the way of successful surgery will be reviewed. Advancing hearing aid technology means that not operating may often be the best option for our patients and issues of consent will be considered.

Ossiculoplasty in the presence of a mobile stapes will be discussed and the author's results using a variety of prostheses presented. His current prosthesis of choice is the KURZ partial clip prosthesis which offers many advantages and gives superior results.

In the absence of a mobile stapes ossiculoplasty is more challenging and achieving stability can be difficult. Footplate shoes and the malleus replacement prosthesis will be discussed with a look at the practical issues involved and achievable results. The issue of performing a stapedotomy through a mobile footplate as a means of achieving medial stability will also be discussed with the few suitable indications described.

Effect of Therapeutic Pulsed Ultrasound on Smell Dysfunction in Subjects with Chronic Rhinosinusitis

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Abstract:

Olfactory dysfunction is one of the main symptoms of chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) caused by bacteria in the form of biofilm. Therapeutic pulsed ultrasound (TPU), which has anti-inflammatory effects and the ability to disrupt the strong walls of biofilms (community of bacteria), can help relieve the symptoms of chronic sinusitis, one of the major symptoms of which is olfactory dysfunction. Methods: A 42-year-old man, who had contracted CRS and whose olfactory sense had subsequently declined gradually in the course of two years, underwent the pulsed ultrasound treatment for ten sessions, (three days a week) on his maxillary and frontal sinuses. CT-Scan and the Sino-Nasal Outcome Test (SNOT-20) questionnaire were employed to measure the severity of the symptoms. Moreover, the Iran Smell Identification Test (Iran-SIT) was employed to measure the degree of olfactory dysfunction. Results: Smell dysfunction and the severity of symptom in CRS relatively improved according to SNOT-20 and ISIT scales by 80% and 41%, respectively.

Conclusion: It appears that TPU can be influential in improving the olfactory dysfunction and other symptoms caused by CRS before and after treatment.

Vestibular Evoked Myogenic Potentials (VEMPs)

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Abstract:

Background: Vestibular evoked myogenic potentials (VEMPs) is a relatively new method of recording function (and dysfunction) from the vestibular nervous system, but is quickly gaining wide acceptance on a global scale. Air-conducted sound can be used to stimulate the otolith organs of the inner ear. Use of this short duration and reproducible stimulus allows one to record high amplitude responses from either the sternocleidomastoid muscle (cervical VEMPs or cVEMPs) or from the inferior oblique muscle (ocular VEMPs or oVEMPs). The former is related predominantly to saccular and inferior vestibular nerve function and its pathway, whilst the latter relates predominantly to utricle and superior vestibular nerve. Bone conducted vibration can also be used to stimulate the otolith organs, and this method has also been found to be highly reproducible. Clinical applications are not restricted to the confirmation of Superior Semicircular Canal Dehiscence Syndrome, but also has been found to be useful for other conditions such as differentiating Vestibular Migraine from Meniere's Disease, and also indicating the presence of conditions that specifically involve either the superior and/or inferior vestibular nerve in the presence of normal caloric responses. Neurological applications include ruling out vestibular neuropathy in the presence of a diffuse peripheral neuropathy, and in determining the nature of vestibular symptoms in other conditions such as multiple sclerosis.

Methods: As a stand-alone lecture, a one hour session is planned. If a hands-on/practical demonstration following the lecture is considered useful, the total time would be expected to be 1.5 hours.

Results: After this teaching course, the audience will be able to practice VEMPs in their own laboratories, using recording equipment that they already have, and to be able to apply the results to help diagnose cases or to be able to explain the results of therapy.

Parents Perceived Quality of Life for Children with Cochlear Implants

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study is to identify the important aspects of quality of life assessed in children with cochlear implant (Figure 1). Parental Perspective questionnaire with modified in Bangla was used as a data collection tool in this study. Data was collected through face to face interview with 25 parents of children with Cochlear Implant (CI) attended at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University, Dhaka. Among 25 cochlear implant children, the boys (12) and girls (13) were nearly the same. Results indicated that the majority of the children had difficulties with communication with known people (48.00%) and before implantation children with CI obtained no benefit at all from hearing aids (76.00%). However, the research finding shows that they are largely satisfied with the outcomes from implantation. Improvement of social relationship, family well-being, within the family, educational condition, and self-reliance was satisfactorily reported by the parents. This study would help the clinician, speech pathologist, children and parents to raise awareness about the impact of CI and its treatment.

Keywords:

Quality of Life, Children, Cochlear Implant

Figure 1: Cochlear implants are electronic devices which have both surgically implanted and externally worn parts. This is designed to enhance hearing abilities [1]. It consists of a receiver/stimulator that is surgically implanted under the skin, behind the ear with a magnet and an electrode array. It is implanted into the cochlea and provides direct electrical stimulation to the nerve fibers. The external parts include a microphone, a speech processor, and a transmitting coil that are placed behind the ear [2].

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Otorhinolaryngological Myiasis: The Problem & Its Presentations In The Weak And Forgotten

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Abstract:

Introduction: Myiasis is more common in tropical regions but now increasing incidence seen in West due to intercontinental travel. Otorhinolaryngological myiasis is rare and seen in diabetics, alcoholic or vegetative patients unable in self-care having decreased sensations.

Material & Methods: Clinical findings and co-morbidities of 67 myiasis cases were noted. Maggots were manually removal, identified and patients managed with ivermectin and antibiotics.

Observations: 33 nasal myiasis, 13 aural myiasis and 5 patients with oral myiasis were seen. Seven patients with head neck wounds myiasis and 9 patients of tracheostome myiasis were managed.

Discussion: Warm humid climate of tropical regions is major concern along with co existing conditions like low socioeconomic status, poor sanitation, Alcoholism, psychiatric diseases and neuropathies. Hesitancy is seen in attendants and health care professionals to deal with myiasis.

Conclusion: Awareness about possible risk factors is important in avoiding myiasis along with prompt treatment which reduces morbidity. Tracheostome myiasis is an under documented entity rather than a rare presentation.

Keywords:

Myiasis, Maggots, Tracheostomy, Larva, Ivermectin, screwworm, *Chrysomya bezziana*, *Musca domestica*, Atrophic rhinitis.

Figure 1: Case of tracheostomy some myiasis

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Pharmacotherapy of Menieres disease (MD) non-conventionally in a tertiary care Neurotology clinic report of a study on 200 patients.

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Abstract:

Meniere's Disease (MD) is not an uncommon cause of vertigo and is characterized by recurrent attacks of head spinning accompanied by fluctuating sensorineural hearing loss, tinnitus and a sense of aural fullness. Prosper Ménière in 1861 attributed the symptoms to a disorder of the inner ear, suggesting that the mechanism to be similar to that of migraine or inner ear vasospasm. Later studies have shown that Meniere's disease is caused by hydrops of the inner ear, rather hydrops (collection of fluid) of the endolymphatic space to be more precise. However, there are lots of controversies till date regarding pathophysiology, investigations and treatment of Meniere's disease. Many scientific committees have recommended certain diagnostic and treatment protocols which have been proved to be inefficient and unscientific later on and their veracity challenged. The treatment of Meniere's disease has remained an enigma forever. One of the most common treatment regimens suggested by different committees is the long continued use of a vestibular suppressant betahistine. However the drug betahistine though commonly recommended by different scientific bodies is itself a very controversial drug and of questionable efficacy. The mechanism of action of Betahistine is not known with certainty and there is no authentic scientific study explaining its exact mechanism of action and how exactly it reduces hydrops which is the believed pathophysiology of Meniere's disease; it is promoted by pharmaceutical companies on some very hypothetical assumptions only many of which are not evidence-based. One recent randomized, double blind, placebo-controlled multi-centric, long-term Class A study on the efficacy of Betahistine in Meniere's disease established that betahistine at recommended dosages and even at reasonably high doses (thrice the recommended therapeutic dose) is nothing more than a placebo. In view of the controversies surrounding the treatment of Meniere's disease, we had carried out a study to evaluate the efficacy of a different therapeutic regime without betahistine or any other vestibular sedative. We share this experience in trying to treat 200 consecutive patients of confirmed Meniere's disease (typical history, Glycerol test and ECoG positive) with a combination of Diuretics, and Migraine prophylactic drugs only. The logic of this therapeutic regime being the fact that Meniere's disease being an endolymphatic hydrops (accumulation of fluid) should justifiably and logically respond to diuretics; and the use of migraine prophylactic drugs is based on the strong association between Meniere's disease and Migraine and the literature support for the common origin of Migraine and Meniere's disease. The outcome of the study is very promising and shows that 88% of all patients showed very good response to the use of diuretics and migraine prophylactic medication. Only 2% patient's needed surgical intervention in the form of intratympanic gentamicin and only one patient had to be sent for vestibular neurectomy. 10% patients needed repeated therapy with vestibular sedatives. The study also reviews relevant literatures to provide justification to the treatment protocol advocated by the author.

Challenges in Management of Paediatric Airway Surgery Services in Nepal

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Abstract:

Paediatric airway surgery is still emerging and challenging for a developing country like Nepal with limited resources.. Though procedures such as cold steel excision of respiratory papillomatosis and rigid bronchoscopy were being done since earlier days of establishment of the department.

Here, I briefly discuss about development and our challenges in managing paediatric airway problem surgery in Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital, Nepal with short discussion and video of few cases.

In May 2014, Hands -on paediatric airway workshop course was organized for the first time with help of a renowned airway surgeon from India with the thought to start airway services.

From 2016/17 onwards , with help of team from United States further development of Various aspects of paediatric airway surgery were explored such as endoscopic evaluation, endoscopic balloon dilatation, cricoid split with graft including different approaches of anesthesia . After introduction of CO2 LASER in Operation Theater management of subglottic stenosis and arytenoidectomy became much rewarding

Though the open surgical procedures are still challenging, endoscopic procedures like web excision using LASER or cold steel, balloon dilatation of laryngeal stenosis, microdebridement of papillomatosis are being done regularly. With ongoing paediatric airway workshops being held every year, various aspects of paediatric airway surgery are yet to be explored and dynamicity of surgical expertise seems to be widening.

Lack of well-equipped intensive care facility with standardized protocols, Paediatric anesthesiologists, well trained nursing staffs are among few restraining factors resulting in unanticipated morbidities and mortalities.